

ELECTRONIC BANKING: ITS ROLE AND DEVELOPMENT IN THE MODERN FINANCIAL SYSTEM

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Abstract

The article talks about the role and development of electronic banking in the modern financial system. The development of information technology has significantly changed the banking sector, providing customers with easy access to financial services and increasing satisfaction. Different types of electronic banking, including internet banking and mobile banking, offer a wide range of services. The history of electronic banking began in the 1960s with the use of ATMs and entered a new phase with the spread of the Internet. Modern electronic banking is characterized by customer convenience, reduced financial costs and data security, but there are also security and regulatory issues. In the future, the development of electronic banking is expected with the introduction of new technologies such as fintech, blockchain and artificial intelligence.

Keywords: electronic banking, financial system, information technology, customer satisfaction, internet banking, mobile banking, security, fintech, blockchain, artificial intelligence.

Introduction

In modern times, the rapid development of information technologies has significantly changed the banking sector. Electronic banking, as a system that provides customers with easier and more convenient access to financial services, has become a platform that makes banks' operations more efficient and increases customer satisfaction. For this reason, the relevance of electronic banking has increased even more today.

In terms of legal framework, electronic banking is supported by appropriate legislative and regulatory frameworks. Laws and regulations promoting the development of electronic banking have been adopted in many countries. This legal framework, in addition to protecting the rights of customers, also regulates the activities of banks. Thus, the legal basis of electronic banking increases its reliability and customer trust.

The importance of electronic banking is directly related to its role in the modern financial system. In addition to providing 24/7 service to customers, this system enables banks to reduce operational costs, improve service quality, and expand their customer base. At the same time, electronic banking allows to serve a wider customer base, increasing financial inclusion.

The purpose of this study is to examine the development, advantages and challenges of electronic banking. The study will provide detailed information about the role of e-banking in modern times, its impact on customer satisfaction and the risks it faces.

Definition and types of electronic banking

Electronic banking is a system that allows customers to access banking services using the Internet and other electronic means. This system enables customers to carry out financial transactions, manage their accounts, make payments and use other services without going to physical bank branches. Electronic banking is aimed at providing more convenient, fast and secure banking services through the application of modern technologies. Its core principles include a user-friendly interface, data security, 24/7 service availability and increased customer satisfaction.

There are following types of electronic banking:

Internet banking: A system that allows customers to manage their bank accounts, make transactions and obtain statements in an online environment. Customers access their accounts through the bank's website (Khan, 2019).

Mobile banking: Applications that allow you to use banking services through a mobile phone or tablet. Mobile banking enables users to carry out financial transactions from anywhere and anytime.

ATMs (Automated Teller Machines): These are self-service terminals that allow customers to withdraw cash, make deposits, check balances and perform other banking transactions.

POS terminals (Point of Sale Terminals): These are devices used at points of sale. Customers can pay with these terminals through bank cards (Chaffey, 2017).

Electronic wallets: These are systems that facilitate financial transactions on various online platforms. These platforms are used for customers to send, receive and pay online (Ghosh, 2014).

These types make the banking process easier and financial transactions more accessible by providing customers with a wider range of services. The development of electronic banking systems increases the quality of financial services in accordance with the requirements of the modern era (Catalini & Gans, 2016).

Historical development of electronic banking

The development of electronic banking dates back to the middle of the 20th century. The first Automated Teller Machines (ATMs) were introduced in the 1960s. This has made banking services more affordable by giving customers access to cash (Ghosh, 2014). In the 1980s, banks began to transition to computer systems for processing and storing customer information. During this period, faster and more accurate data management increased the quality of banking services (Akhter, 2021).

The spread of the Internet in the 1990s ushered in a new phase of electronic banking. Customers now

have access to online banking services. The first internet banking platform was launched in 1994 (Khan, 2019). This era made the banking process even easier by providing customers with 24/7 service.

The impact of information technology on the banking sector is wide and multifaceted. Automation has increased the speed of operations and reduced human errors (Chaffey, 2017). The development of the Internet has made it possible for customers to carry out financial transactions whenever they want.

The rise of mobile banking started with the widespread use of mobile phones. In the early 2000s, mobile applications made it even easier for customers to access banking services. Mobile banking was not limited to account management but also included payments, money transfers and investment transactions.

In recent years, the emergence of blockchain and cryptocurrencies has begun to reshape the banking sector. These technologies enable the emergence of new financial services by increasing the transparency and security of transactions (Catalini & Gans, 2016).

In general, the historical development of electronic banking is closely related to the introduction of modern technologies into the banking sector. Each advancement has enabled customers to use services more efficiently and has played an important role in improving banking services. This process is still ongoing and will continue to evolve as new innovations emerge in the future.

Electronic banking has many advantages:

Customer convenience

One of the biggest advantages of electronic banking is customer convenience. Customers can access banking services 24 hours a day, 7 days a week. This ensures that they can carry out their financial transactions whenever they want, thus eliminating the need to visit physical bank branches. Research shows that online banking makes it easier for customers to use services and saves them more time (Liao & Cheung, 2002).

Reducing financial costs

Electronic banking systems allow banks to significantly reduce transaction costs. Automated systems minimize human intervention, increasing the speed and efficiency of operations. This allows banks to provide more profitable services to customers by reducing costs. Also, for customers, the use of electronic services results in lower commission costs than traditional services.

Data security

Electronic banking systems implement various security measures to ensure the security of customer information. These measures include encryption, two-factor authentication, and regular security updates. Such measures increase the protection of customer data and financial transactions (Zhou et al., 2010). Research shows that customers' trust in e-banking services is directly related to banks' adherence to security standards.

Challenges and risks of electronic banking

Electronic banking has become an integral part of the modern financial system. However, there are a number of challenges and risks in this area. Three main

aspects of these challenges - security issues, customer trust and regulatory issues - will be discussed below.

Security issues: One of the most serious challenges of electronic banking is security issues. Cyber attacks pose a serious threat to banking systems and customer information. Since 2020, the number of cyber attacks has increased; Among these attacks, DDoS (Distributed Denial of Service) attacks, phishing and malware are widespread (Kaspersky, 2021).

Data protection is also important in this context. Leakage of customer data can seriously damage the credibility of banks. In 2019, the Capital One bank data breach resulted in the exposure of over 100 million customer data (Capital One, 2019). Such incidents make it necessary for banks to implement stricter security measures to protect customer data.

Customer trust: Customer trust is a critical factor for the success of e-banking. Customers should trust the security of their data and the trustworthiness of the bank when using online banking services. Research shows that customer trust is important for banks to expand their customer base and increase customer satisfaction (Gao et al., 2018).

In order to increase customer trust, banks should take measures such as protecting customer data, transparency and improving the quality of customer services. At the same time, informing customers about security measures can help build their confidence.

Regulatory issues: Regulation of electronic banking is essential to ensure the health of the modern financial system. Regulatory authorities should create legislative frameworks to ensure banks adhere to security standards, protect customer data and prevent financial crimes. The GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) law of the European Union has put forward strict requirements for the protection of customer data (European Commission, 2018).

At the same time, regulatory authorities should also consider the use of new technologies (for example, blockchain and cryptocurrencies). In addition to increasing the transparency of the banking system, these technologies can also create new risks (Zohar, 2015). Therefore, regulatory authorities should monitor the development of modern technologies and create appropriate regulatory frameworks.

Although electronic banking has led to revolutionary changes in the presentation of financial services in modern times, it also brings out a number of challenges and risks. Security issues, customer trust and regulatory issues are the most important aspects in this area. Banks must strengthen security measures to gain and maintain customer trust and adhere to appropriate regulatory frameworks to protect customer data.

The future of electronic banking

Electronic banking, as a dynamic part of the modern financial system, is developing rapidly. This development is shaped by the introduction of new technologies, changes in customer requirements and the influence of market dynamics. Below, the main trends and perspectives that determine the future of electronic banking will be discussed.

Trends

Fintech: The Fintech (financial technology) sector plays an important role in the development of electronic banking. Fintech companies improve customer satisfaction by making traditional banking services faster, cheaper and more accessible. As of 2021, fintech investments have surpassed \$100 billion worldwide (KPMG, 2021). The introduction of Fintech not only improves the customer experience, but also reduces the operational costs of banks.

Blockchain: Blockchain technology is widely used to provide transparency and security in electronic banking. This technology facilitates the recording and tracking of financial transactions, and at the same time, reduces the risk of fraud (Catalini & Gans, 2016). The implementation of blockchain also makes bank operations more efficient through the use of smart contracts.

Artificial intelligence: Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning are used to improve customer service and risk management. AI helps to provide personalized offers and detect fraud by analyzing customer behavior (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2017). Meanwhile, chatbots and virtual assistants improve customer satisfaction by providing 24/7 customer service.

Future prospects

The future of electronic banking is full of predictions. First of all, the customer-centric approach will come to the fore. Banks will increasingly use data analytics and AI to provide services tailored to customer requirements. This will enhance customer experience as well as strengthen customer trust (Deloitte, 2020).

Second, the development of the regulatory environment will enable the further expansion of electronic banking. Regulatory authorities should create legislative frameworks that facilitate the use of fintech and blockchain technologies. This will help banks provide innovative services and expand their customer base (World Economic Forum, 2021).

In recent times, electronic banking is expected to spread even more globally. The growth of mobile banking services in developing countries will increase financial inclusion. This will enable it to serve a wider customer base (GSMA, 2021).

The future of electronic banking is shaped by the application of new technologies such as fintech, blockchain and artificial intelligence. A customer-centric approach, development of the regulatory environment and global expansion will accelerate the development of electronic banking. Banks should follow these trends and develop their strategic approach to increase customer satisfaction and gain advantage in market competition.

Conclusion

Electronic banking, as an integral part of the modern financial system, has caused revolutionary changes in the presentation of banking services. This system aims to reduce banks' operational costs and increase customer satisfaction, while providing customers with faster, more convenient and more accessible financial services. The development of electronic banking creates new opportunities to increase customer trust, address security issues and improve the regulatory environment.

At the same time, the future of e-banking is getting stronger with the introduction of new technologies such as fintech, blockchain and artificial intelligence. These technologies help banks provide customer services more efficiently and transparently, while protecting customer data (Catalini & Gans, 2016; Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2017).

Recommendations

Security Investments: Banks should invest in modern security technologies to protect customer data. Against the background of increasing cyber attacks, stricter security measures must be implemented to protect customer data (Kaspersky, 2021).

Customer Centric Approach: Banks should use data analytics and artificial intelligence to provide services tailored to customer requirements. This will increase customer satisfaction and strengthen customer trust (Deloitte, 2020).

Regulatory Cooperation: Banks should cooperate with regulatory authorities to support the creation of legislative frameworks that facilitate the use of new technologies. This will accelerate the introduction of innovative services (World Economic Forum, 2021).

Recommendations for Customers

When using electronic banking services, customers should consider the following measures to ensure the security of their information:

Use of strong passwords: Customers should choose strong and unique passwords for accessing their accounts. The password should be at least 8-12 characters long and should contain upper and lower case letters, numbers and special characters.

Two-factor authentication: Two-factor authentication (2FA) must be enabled. This is an additional layer of security when accessing your account, and knowing your password alone is not enough. For example, you may be asked to enter a code sent to your mobile phone.

Suspicious Activity Tracking: Customers should contact their bank immediately when they see suspicious activity on their accounts. This will help prevent unauthorized access.

Secure internet connection: E-banking services should be accessed only through a reliable and secure internet connection. Caution should be exercised when using public Wi-Fi networks, as these networks are more vulnerable.

Information Update: It is important to regularly monitor the security information and updates provided by the banks. Banks can send newsletters to customers informing them about security measures and new services.

Implementing these measures will help customers use electronic banking services more securely.

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